

IMPLEMENTING INTERNET RESOURCES IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: English language skills here mean the development of the main parts or elements of the language which include speaking, listening, reading, and writing. English language subject has different educational tools that are likely suited with it. Smartphone and internet usage have actively influence daily life, even for children and adolescents. In learning activity, smartphone is a tool to help students connected to be online. A qualitative approach was pursued in this study. Then, the data collection technique used in this study is a survey by using questionnaires. As result, the research shows that most students spend much time to access the social network, some students access internet for dictionary and games, and only a few students access internet for education purposes. In short, the students rather to use smartphone for other thing than education.

Keywords: smartphone, internet, English language learning.

INTRODUCTION

Most children and adolescents in Indonesia are now actively using internet. Internet is needed for them to study or just to communicate with families and their friends around the world. Internet does provide a powerful genuine resource for the learning of English. As Warschauer (2001) reveals that internet may be said to enhance English language learning in accordance to communicative language teaching principles on meaningful interaction. This shows that internet has essential effect to English learning which is to activate communicative skill. In this case, students' roles are required to be more dominant on English language learning process to catch knowledge from various resources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Smartphone and internet usage have influence human daily life, even for children and adolescents. The way people learn English has also shifted from the traditional classroom to the internet. Many apps and website are available to learn and explore the language. With updating reason, teacher prepared materials (texts, audio-visual, video, pictures, etc.) to support students to learn English in classroom. So, many exercises are adopted as if they are authentic one in learning process.

Furthermore, McLuhan (2012) states some advantages of online learning as follows:

- 1) Access – the internet offers the possibility to experience English without the need of travel. Even without the need of leaving home or bedroom.
- 2) Flexibility – the internet allows for students to learn language whenever they want and wherever they want.
- 3) Response – the internet offers the possibility of instant feedback to learners. This greatly enhances the learning experience.
- 4) Repeatability – the learner can encounter the language in a repetitive fashion until mastery is achieved.
- 5) Durability – the internet is 24/7. It never tires. It does not take coffee breaks.
- 6) Modality – the internet is a multi-modal learning tool. It stimulates in a rich sensory and cognitive and thus fertilizes language acquisition successfully.
- 7) Specificity – the internet allows the language learner choose in both what and with who will be learned. Learning can be tailored to the language learners' precise makeup and needs.
- 8) Cost – the internet is a business model which due to economies of scale can offer services for pennies. It also offers to widen access through a pay as you can dynamic.

In brief, internet allows students to share not only brief messages, but also create lengthy documents – thus facilitating collaborative writing (learning). Besides, learners can share graphics, sounds and video. Thus, the internet does help teacher in creating an environment where authentic and creative communication is integrated into all aspects of the course.

The results of many researches show that most students spend much time to access social network and other, some students access internet for dictionary and games, and only a few students access internet for education purposes. In short, the students were rather to use smartphone for other thing than education. The media used by them in order to support their learning including making tasks, projects, or other assignments, especially in the development of English language skills.

CONCLUSION

Internet is a media to help teachers and students to get much materials, enrich teacher's pedagogy when selecting the material and methods in English learning, and engage the students in creating a new English learning experience.

Based on the result of the data analysis, most students spend much time to access the social network and other, some students access internet for dictionary and games, and only a few students access internet for education purposes. In short, the students were rather to use smartphone for other thing than education.

English language learning should be focused on leading language teaching by using English resources from smartphone and internet, as media, which closed to students. By using smartphone and internet, it is expected that either teacher or students become more active and creative to explore their knowledge through media.

Pedagogically, there is an urgent need for teachers to implement smartphone-based language learning in order to engage students to be critics with material and its content. So, it enables students to build and enhance a technology awareness of smartphone and internet usage on English language learning in classroom.

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